

TALENT MANAGEMNT IN EDUCATION SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

Attract, develop and retain employees by assured pipeline of knowledgeable and qualifying people is important for the success of the institutions which is known as talent management. The main issues facing by the educational institutes is shortage of competent and qualified faculties. It has resulted in institutions focusing on how to retain the talent and how to develop them. Where institutions are running at risk of talent crisis talent retention is the not only the choice of the managers but also the need for the institutions. The important factors which contributes to faculty retention and recruitment are benefits, supportive environments, spouse employment opportunities, start-up and resources and salaries. This research paper provides few strategies which institutions can adopt for attracting and retaining talent which is best available for them.

KEYWORDS

Talent Retention, Talent Acquisition and Talent Development, Education Sector, Strategies.

1. INTRODUCTION

For many institutions, the talent management is relatively untapped and new concept in the field of human resource management despite of proving many times its importance and competitive advantage for the institution. Institutions doesn't have knowledge of related to the strategies used in talent management which are deployed in higher education system to support them and the effectiveness of those strategies. Industries and corporates are concerned with the talents to make the business stand in the competitive era.

There is a 25% difference shown in attrition rate which results in million\$ expenses of organization to replace several professionals for every 50th person position in the organization. (jonathan et al,2011) . talent management is increasing its importance in corporate human resource management which defines it is more profitable and feasible to develop talent instead of acquiring and hiring talent from the outside.[20]

Talent management hold 3 different conceptions according to (lewis and heckmen's 2006): 1) collection of practices of human resource department, 2) human resources flow within the organization, and 3) rewarding, sourcing and developing talent of the employee. Nurturing and leveraging the asset of talent management for the continuous growth is very important for the organization well being and it hold equal importance as serving in the corporate sector to someone serve in the education field.[16]

Gay and sims (2006) introduces talent management as career progress and facilitating development of highly skilled and talent individuals which uses formalized resources, procedures, processes and policies.[1]

The growth of the education sector totally depend on the various kind of the employee which retain as a faculty. It's the faculty who sets the image and tone of the institution to move ahead. Therefore, the hiring of the right faculty becomes challenge for the institutions of the education and high turnover is a big threat in the organizations.[13]

The loss of the faculty suddenly impacts on the existing ongoing academic plans in negative terms which resulted into mostly institutions failed to assist managerial staff for the skill .the purpose of the study to conduct is to review the process of talent management followed by institutions and identifying factors which influence faculties to stay in the organization. It also provides the conceptual framework of employee retention of talented one.[3]

2. REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

2.1 TALENT

Talent is defined as the ones people in corporations who can develop differences in the organizational performance either by their instant contribution or by demonstrating the best stage of capability in the long run. (McCartney &Worman, 2013; Bhatnagar, 2007)[6]. The term talent also describes as the employees who are technically and globally literate and agile operationally which refer as the brightest and best employees falling in the top 10%-20% of member of organization accordance to the value represent as "A" players in the institution. (Beechler& Woodward, 2009)

Therefore, talent represents as those who possess relevant skills, good judgement, character, right attitude knowledge and experience plus the members willing to grow, learn and demonstrates commitment in the organization Michaelis et al (2001).[2]

2.2 TALENT MANAGEMENT

Managing the employee talent is). Always identified as a major strategic issue in the institutions. (Clark, 2009)The reason behind this is organizations mostly fails to redefine the value proposition of their employee which created issues in attracting, retaining and developing the top bets talent (Ernst & Young, 2010)[5]. The term talent management is conceptualized by different person in different ways.

Talent management is a systemized attraction, retention/engagement and development of people of high value in the organization(McCartney &Worman, 2013; Lawler, 2008; Smyley& Wenzel, 2006; Campbell & smith, 2010; MOR, n.d.). Talent management also termed as the process which deals with the development and identification of all the talent especially of high potential talent for the future projects, positions and assignments. (Clark, 2009; Cobb, 2007). Another more illuminating definition of talent management is that it is a dynamic, ongoing process of systematically identifying, assessing and developing talent for future critical roles to ensure continuity and optimal organizational performance (Heidke, 2006). The process of talent management focuseson developing leaders and employees for the better future of the organization (Gay & Sims, 2006). [11]

2.3 AICTE AND UGC NORMS – FACULTY STUCTURE

The skills, knowledge, values and attitudes of staff count as the aspects which contributes to both the effectiveness of the individual and performance of the organization.In addition with the norms on structure and pattern of the staff, there should be guidelines which emphasizes for the process

of development, recruitment and performance appraisal. The ratio for assistant professors to associate professors to professors should be 6:2:1 in the undergraduate colleges and in post graduate colleges the ratio to assistant professors to associate professors should be 2:1.[12] It helps in assisting institutions which are not able to define programmes to get ensure related to hiring appropriate senior faculty at the undergraduate level also.[18]

2.4 PRACTICES

In today's world businesses are adopting software's like service (SaaS) applications which helps in doing several tasks such as invoicing, accounting and collaboration etc. giving importance to talent management and human resource applications (Corsello, 2012). [10]

Talent management helps in improving learning, employee benefits, competence compensation, development, employee engagement etc. Talent management helps in providing ways to measure productivity and absenteeism turnover outcomes (Mudoli, 2008). There are different approaches such as INCLUSIVE APPROACH, FUTURE LEADER APPROACH, BLENDED APPROACH, EXECUTIVE TALENT POOL APPROACH, SUCCESSION PLANNING APPROACH helps in practicing management in the institution (UK commission for Employment & Skills, 2012).[7]

2.5 CAUSES FOR EMPLOYEE TURNOVER IN THE INSTITUTIONS

The stress and fear comes in the mind of academic employees due to several reasons, they are:-

- Work overload
- Job insecurity
- Role ambiguity
- Insufficient reward and recognition
- Insufficient resources and funding
- Poor practice of management
- Role erosion and inadequacy

2.6 WAYS TO RETAIN TALENT IN INSTITUTION

- Many educational institutes launched development of faculty programs to shape and improve the career and personality of their employees.
- Policies and procedures should be well informed in beginning to the respective faculties of the institution.
- They should give rewards and motivate the employees according to their performance.
- At least 3 week orientation program should be conducted for the employees to make them thorough with the work of every department. Senior guide should also be provided to help as a mentor and friend to the employee to make him/her comfortable.
- The equal opportunities should be given to both senior and junior members to raise voice for any concerns and should be ask to provide feedback by annual meetings.
- To make them feel understandable and good gifts should be distributed at the time of festivals to boost their morale and to maintain healthy relationships.

- Leaves like maternity or paternity leaves should be provided for different time period for the birth of the child or adoption case.
- Continuous learning must be provided in the organization to their employees through learning games and activities every week so that they can learn something new every week and it helps them in self-development.
- Salary and different ways of compensating the outstanding performance must be done in the organization.
- Get a strategic view clearly of strengths and weaknesses, workforce potential, and specialized skills.
- The flexibility should be generated to accommodate and balancing the need of work and family so that they can easily contribute and give their best to the productivity of the institution.
- Assistance for External grants provision for researches and other purpose should be given.

2.7 EMPLOYEE RETENTION STRATEGIES

- Communication :- In organization, communication should be done properly, nobody should feel left out. Every policies and programmes must be communicated properly and feedback should also be taken.[19]
- Right selection: institution should hire right employee for the right job so that employees can work with whole heartedly and give their best with high motivation and greater zeal which ultimately leads to increasing productivity as they will remain in company for long.
- Provide opportunities development and growth: learning should be an inseparable part for faculties in an organization so that they can develop new skills and knowledge in themselves. If employees feels boredom at job they will lose interest to work.
- Performance-based bonus: the employees who are more productive in an organization must get more remuneration so that they can work more and their performance get recognized which can be arranged by cutting the hikes salary.
- Equitable and fair treatment for every employee: The surest ways to build resentment and animosity in an organization can be to allow preferential treatment and favoritism of individual team members.
- Including juniors in decision-making: subordinates and juniors should be included in the process of decision making which can help in creating a sense of involvement and leads to generating new ideas.
- Accountability: there should be an environment of transparency and accountability helps employees which helps in equality feeling with their superiors and building emotional bonding too among employees.

3. RECOMMENDATIONS

From the above study about talent management in higher education institutes, it can be recommended:-

- In education institutes, institutional managers should be accountable for taking care of problems regarding talent management which will ultimately helps in solving those issues with faculties and maintaining good and healthy relationships among them.[8]
- Institutions managers should spend their more time in matters regarding talent management and how to retain their employees.
- Talent management strategies must be adopted in the institutions which will help in learning and growth of their employees making faculties more satisfy with their jobs and tasks.
- The issues regarding talent management must be discussed in the meetings of the institutions on the priority basis to make them understand the importance of managing the talent in the institutions.

4. CONCLUSION

From the above study we can conclude that talent management in the institutions can really help in identification of the right talent, development of that talent and retaining that talent in the institution for its success and growth [9]. Therefore, we can say that managing the talent will lead to development and growth of the organization.

It is also concluded that if talent management strategies are adopted in educational institutions will helps in the identification of the core competencies required for the job description by the faculties hence helps in the management by recruiting and selecting the most effective employees based on the suitable competencies which will lead to the right job to right person. It is the saying that the recruiting effective person is the first step towards effective retention. Youth is generation is the future of the India who all dependent on the teachers who educate and make them learn in the institutions, therefore it is important to hire, develop and retain the right person for the job.

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